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ABSTRACT

The aim of the actual research is the diagnosis of the organizational effectiveness in the public sector in Albania and Kosovo. The research will be focused only on two public institutions, one in Kosovo and one in Albania. The Organizational Diagnosis Questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was based on the Weisbord Six-Box organizational diagnosis model which includes six components: purpose, structure, rewards, relationship, helpful mechanisms and leadership. The results of the questionnaire analysis are necessary to understand what the employees think of each component (informal aspect). To better understand the formal aspect, interviews were conducted with the managers of each institution. Then the results were compared to find the existing gaps between the formal and informal aspect. In the Albanian public institution, the formal and informal aspect was not compatible for the "Relationship" and "Reward" component. In the Kosovo public institution, the formal and informal aspect was not compatible for the "Relationship", "Leadership", "Helpful Mechanisms" and "Reward" component. The results of the study showed that in these public institutions did not exist serious problems regarding work division, clarity of organizational goals, leadership style, reward system, conflicts between individuals and working units, helpful mechanisms and ability to change. It can be concluded that the organizational effectiveness is a little higher in the public institution in Albania than in the public institution in Kosovo.

KEYWORDS: public institutions, effectiveness, Weisbord Six-Box model, organizational diagnosis

INTRODUCTION

The recent business environment is becoming more competitive and dynamic. Customers require more choices, better prices, high quality and better post-sale services. Technology is changing quickly and if you do not catch the last trends, you may probably lose competitive advantage. Firms cannot satisfy customers and be at the leading edge of technology if suppliers are not reliable and consistent with the supply of materials (Chen and Paulraj, 2003). Therefore, firms have to improve their organizational effectiveness, in order to survive and ensure success in this hyper-competitive and uncertain environment.

Organizational effectiveness is a critical concept in the management literature, but it doesn't exist a universal well-accepted definition. According to Drucker (2006), effectiveness means doing the right thing and accomplishing the goals successfully. A more recent definition is offered by Kreitner & Cassidy (2012:245): "Organizational effectiveness can be defined as meeting organizational objectives and prevailing societal expectations in the near future, adapting and developing in the intermediate future, and surviving in the distant future".

Many organizational development strategies exist for improving organizational effectiveness. One of these strategies is organizational diagnosis which presents the assessment of the current situation of an organization in order to identify the most appropriate interventions for its future development (Stegerean, Gavrea, & Marin, 2010: 3). There are many organizational diagnosis models: Force Field Analysis, Leavitt's Model, Mc Kinsey 7S Framework, Congruence Model, Weisbord's Six Box Model and many others (Falleta, 2005). In this study, the last model will be used (Weisbord's Six Box Model) because it is the most used in practice and empirical studies due to its simplicity. Its main disadvantage is that it does not consider directly the influence of the external environment.

The state fulfills its basic functions through the public sector and delivers public goods which cannot be produced by the private sector. The public officials should ensure to their citizens that the management of the public sector and the delivery of public goods is done effectively. As a result questions about the effectiveness of the public sector are raised often, and so an analysis of the organizational effectiveness of this sector will be worth studying (Ziebicki, 2013).

The aim of the actual research is the diagnosis of the organizational effectiveness of the public sector in Albania and Kosovo. The research will be focused only on two public institutions, one in Kosovo and one in Albania, whose names will not be mentioned to respect the anonymity of the respondent. The Organizational Diagnosis Questionnaire was used and also interviews were conducted with the main managers of these institutions.

The outline of the paper is the following: After the introduction section there is the literature review section, where the relevant literature regarding organizational diagnosis and Weisbord's Six Box Model will be analyzed. Then the research methodology is explained. After the research findings are discussed and lastly the conclusions and recommendations are presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational diagnosis models

Weisbord (1976) described the organizational diagnosis as one of the most effective organizational development strategies that help the company to determine gaps between current and desired performance. Beer and Spector (1993) defined organizational diagnosis as "a process that helps an organization to highlight its capabilities and change the nonfunctional aspects of its culture and behavior paths as the basis for a very good effectiveness and continuous improvement.

According to Lowman (2005), the organizational diagnostic process is influenced by three basic questions: What does the practitioner diagnose? With what purpose? and Using what system? Organizational diagnosis has two main purposes: one is the evaluation of organizational dysfunctions and the other is the evaluation of the current state of the organization. The company should first diagnose its actual situation in order to improve its performance.

Organizational diagnosis is important because if we want to design an effective organization first we have to understand the current one. Organizational diagnostic models help the managers to categorize data and to enhance the understanding of organizational problems. In this way, they can make systematic data interpretation and provide appropriate change strategies (Look & Crawford, 2000).

There are many organizational diagnosis models, and some of them are rather old but they are widely used in practice and empirical studies. According to Howard (1994) the choice of the model depends on three criteria:

- ✓ Ease of use: The model chosen should be well understood by the user and the latter feels better with it.
- ✓ Adequacy with the organization: The model should be inclusive enough to cover many aspects of the organization and clear enough for members to give the right answer.
- ✓ Finally, the chosen model should be versatile to allow us to collect information about the organization, where according to the parameters of the model we should not lose any key information.

According to Jones and Brazzel (2006), the Weisbord's Six-Box model was the most used in practice. In the actual study, this model will be used, due to its simplicity in collecting and interpreting the data.

Weisbord's Six-Box Model

This model was developed by an American analyst, Marvin Weisbord. It is called the Six-Box model because the model includes six components: purpose, structure, rewards, relationship, helpful mechanisms and leadership. For each box, diagnosis questions should be posed in order to understand what is happening and what should happen.

Table 1: The Weisbord's Six-Box Model

Components	Explanation	Diagnosis questions
Purpose	It refers to the organization's mission and goals and the extent to which the member of the organization accept, understand and support the firm's purpose.	Do organizational members agree with and support the organization's mission and goals?
Structure	It refer to the way in which the organization is organized; this may be by function – where specialists work together – or by product, program, or project – where multi-skilled teams work together. The aim of this box is to understand if there is a fit between the internal structure and the purpose of the company.	Is there a fit between the purpose and the internal structure of the organization?
Relationships	<i>Relationships</i> focus on who should deal with whom about what and what the quality of those relationships is. There are three main types of work relationships: between people, between work units doing different tasks, and between people and the technology they are using.	What types of relations exist between individuals, between departments, and between individuals and the nature of their jobs? Is their interdependence? What is the quality of relations? What are the modes of conflict?
Rewards	<i>Rewards</i> are the intrinsic and extrinsic rewards people associate with their work. It is important to compare the organizational formal rewards and the perceived reward by the employees.	What does the organization formally reward, and for what do organizational members feel they are rewarded and punished? What does the organization need to do to fit with the environment?
Helpful mechanisms	<i>Helpful mechanisms</i> are the planning, controlling, budgeting, and information systems that serve to meet organizational goals.	Do leaders define purposes? Do they embody purposes in their programs? What is the normative style of leadership?
Leadership	<i>The leadership box</i> refers to typical leadership tasks, including the balance between the other boxes – hence it is intentionally positioned in the center of the model.	Do these mechanisms help or hinder the accomplishment of organizational objectives?

Source: Adapted from Weisbord (1976)

To better understand the model, two premises should be explained. The first premise refers to formal versus informal systems. The bigger the gap between the formal and informal systems within the organization, the less effective the organization is. The second premise concerns the fit between the organization and the external requirements (external demands or pressures as customers, government, and unions) (Falleta, 2005).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As mentioned above the research will be focused on two public institutions, one in Kosovo and one in Albania, whose names will not be mentioned to respect the anonymity of the respondent. The units of the analysis were the employees of these companies (nearly 40 % of the employees answer to the questionnaire). The Organizational Diagnosis Questionnaire (Preziosi, 1980) was distributed to the employees, while face to face interviews were conducted with the managers. The questionnaire was mainly based on the Weisbord Six- Box model. Preziosi

(1980) just added a new box called attitude toward change. The questionnaire consists of 35 questions and each question is related with one of the seven components (refer to Table 2)

Table 2: Organizational Diagnosis Questionnaire

Component	Questions
Purpose	Q1-The goals of this organization are clearly stated. Q8 -I am personally in agreement with the stated goals of my work unit. Q15- I understand the purpose of this organization. Q22- The priorities of this organization were understood by its employees. Q29 - I had enough input in deciding my work-unit goals
Structure	Q2- The division of labor of this organization is flexible. Q9 - The division of labor in this organization is intended to help it reach its goals. Q16- The manner in which work tasks are divided is a logical one. Q23 - The structure of my work unit is well designed. Q30- The division of labor in this organization actually helps it to reach its goals
Relationships	Q4- My relationship with my supervisor was a Harmonious one. Q11- I can always talk with someone at work if I have a work-related problem. Q18- My relationships with members of my work group are friendly as well as professional. Q25- I have established the relationships that I need to do my job properly. Q32- There is no evidence of unresolved conflict in this organization
Rewards	Q5- My job offers me the opportunity to grow as a person. Q12- The pay scale and benefits of this organization treat each employee equitably. Q19 - The opportunity for promotion exists in this organization. Q26 - The salary that I receive is commensurate with the job that I perform. Q33 - All tasks to be accomplished are associated with incentives
Helpful mechanisms	Q6- My immediate supervisor has ideas that are helpful to me and my work group. Q13 I have the information that I need to do a good job. Q20- This organization has adequate mechanisms for binding itself together. Q27- Other work units are helpful to my work unit whenever assistance is requested. Q34- This organization's planning and control efforts are helpful to its growth and development
Leadership	Q3- My immediate supervisor is supportive of my efforts. Q10 - The leadership norms of this organization help its progress. Q17- This organization's leadership efforts result in the organization's fulfillment of its purposes. Q24- It is clear to me whenever my boss is attempting to guide my work efforts. Q31- I understand my boss's efforts to influence me and the other members of the work unit.
Attitude toward change	Q7- This organization is not resistant to change. Q14 - This organization introduces enough new policies and procedures. Q21- This organization favors change. Q28- Occasionally I like to change things about my job. Q35- This organization has the ability to change

Respondents were asked to indicate their current views of their organization on a scale of 1 to 7, where:

- 1- strongly agree
- 2- agree
- 3- agree slightly
- 4- neutral
- 5-disagree slightly
- 6-disagree
- 7- strongly disagree

After the data were collected, the arithmetic mean for each question and for each component was calculated.

According to Preziosi (1980), the results over 4 would indicate a problem with the organizational function. The closer to 7, more severe will be the problem. Results under 4 shows the absence of a problem, with an average close to 1 indicates optimal functioning. It is important to analyze even the relationships between different components.

The results of the questionnaire analysis are necessary to understand what the employees think of each component. To better understand the formal aspect, interviews were conducted with the managers of each institution. The main questions that were asked were:

- ✓ How clear are the company's goals? Are the goals written?
- ✓ What type of organizational structure is used?
- ✓ How are the conflicts solved? Do you have unsolved conflicts?
- ✓ How does the reward system work?
- ✓ Do they exist mechanism that helps the employees to achieve their objectives, like meetings, manuals etc?
- ✓ What is the normative style of leadership?

The research findings of the questionnaire were compared with the information collected by the interviews. In this way, a comparison between the formal and informal aspects of the organizational was easily conducted.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Once the data were collected, they were analyzed with SPSS. The mean of each question and component of the Weisbord model was calculated. In this section each element will be analyzed separately. In table 3 are presented the results for the first element, purpose.

Table 3: Results for the "Purpose" component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q1-The goals of this organization are clearly stated.	2	2.1
Q8 -I am personally in agreement with the stated goals of my work unit.	2.5	2.3
Q15- I understand the purpose of this organization.	2.3	1.6
Q22- The priorities of this organization were understood by its employees.	2.9	3.5
Q29-I had enough input in deciding my work-unit goals	2.3	3
Purpose	2.4	2.5

The mean of each question is less than the neutral result (4). This means that the organizational goals, purpose and priorities are clearly stated, the employees understand and support them. In the public institution in Kosovo, many employees declared that the information provided by the managers regarding the priorities of the institution was not clearly understood. In table 4 are presented the results for the second element, structure.

Table 4: Results for the "Structure" component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q2- The division of labor of this organization is flexible.	2.8	3.5
Q9 - The division of labor in this organization is intended to help it reach its goals.	2.7	2.3
Q16- The manner in which work tasks are divided is a logical one.	3.5	3.4
Q23 - The structure of my work unit is well designed.	2.8	2.3
Q30- The division of labor in this organization actually helps it to reach its goals	2.3	2.3
Structure	2.9	2.8

The employees of these institutions declared that the division of labor is helpful for the achievement of the organizational goals and the structure of the work is well designed. The employees in both the institution thought that the tasks are not divided in a logical way. According to the results of the questionnaire the division of labor is more flexible in the public institution in Albania compared to the one in Kosovo. In table 5 are presented the results for the third element, relationships.

Table 5: Results for the “Relationship” component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q4- My relationship with my supervisor was a harmonious one.	2.3	3.2
Q11- I can always talk with someone at work if I have a work-related problem.	3.6	2.8
Q18- My relationships with members of my work group are friendly as well as professional.	2.6	2
Q25- I have established the relationships that I need to do my job properly.	2.3	2
Q32-There is no evidence of unresolved conflict in this organization	3.1	2.5
Relationships	2.8	2.5

The employees in the public institution in Albania declared that they have good relationships with their supervisors, but they have problems in discussing their problems with the other employees. They accepted that some conflicts are not still resolved, especially conflict between the employees. The employees in the public institution in Kosovo declared that they have a better relationship with the colleagues than with the supervisor. In table 6 are presented the results for the fourth element, rewards.

Table 6: Results for the “Reward” component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q5- My job offers me the opportunity to grow as a person.	2.6	2.6
Q12- The pay scale and benefits of this organization treat each employee equitably.	3.4	4.1
Q19 - The opportunity for promotion exists in this organization.	2.9	3.2
Q26-The salary that I receive is commensurate with the job that I perform.	3.2	2.8
Q33-All tasks to be accomplished are associated with incentives	2.7	2.8
Rewards	3	3.1

The mean of the questions related to the reward component is higher compared with the other questions. It can be noticed that not every employee is treated equitably and as a result, some are paid more even if they work less than the others and also the opportunity for promotion is bigger for them. This is a common problem in the public institution in Kosovo and Albania, because the recruitment process is not fair and transparent. In table 7 are presented the results for the fifth element, helpful mechanisms.

Table 7: Results for the “Helpful mechanism” component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q6- My immediate supervisor has ideas that are helpful to me and my work group.	2.6	3.6
Q13- I have the information that I need to do a good job.	2.5	2.9
Q20- This organization has adequate mechanisms for binding itself together.	2.8	3.5
Q27- Other work units are helpful to my work unit whenever assistance is requested.	3.1	2.8
Q34- This organization’s planning and control efforts are helpful to its growth and development.	2.1	2.2
Helpful mechanisms	2.6	3

The employees of the public institution in Albania accepted that helpful mechanism exists and they help them to achieve the organizational goals. Some of them declared that the necessary assistance was not always offered by the other working units. The employees of the public institution in Kosovo thought that the existing helpful mechanisms were not sufficient for achieving the organizational goals and the supervisors were not always helpful. In table 8 are presented the results for the sixth element, leadership.

Table 8: Results for the “Leadership” component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q3- My immediate supervisor is supportive of my efforts.	2.5	2.4
Q10 - The leadership norms of this organization help its progress.	2.8	2.2
Q17- This organization’s leadership efforts result in the organization’s fulfillment of its purposes.	2.6	3.2
Q24- It is clear to me whenever my boss is attempting to guide my work efforts.	2.8	3.6
Q31- I understand my boss’s efforts to influence me and the other members of the work unit.	2.6	3.3
Leadership	2.7	3

It can be noticed that in the public institution in Albania the leaders support their employees and help the company to improve its performance. The same thing cannot be said for the public institution in Kosovo, as the employees declare that their boss is not always supportive and his efforts sometimes imposes limits to the achievement of the organizational goals. In table 9 are presented the results for the last element, attitude toward change.

Table 9: Results for the “Attitude toward change” component

	Arithmetic mean	
	Albania	Kosovo
Q7-This organization is not resistant to change.	2.9	3.2
Q14 -This organization introduces enough new policies and procedures.	3	3.3
Q21- This organization favors change.	3.1	3.2
Q28- Occasionally I like to change things about my job.	2.6	1.8
Q35-This organization has the ability to change	2.5	2.8
Attitude toward change	2.8	2.9

We can say that the organizations have the ability to change in order to satisfy the external requirements. The Albanian institution is more favorable to the change.

These results showed what really happen inside the organization (informal aspect). Interviews were conducted with the main managers to get information about the formal aspect (what they pretend are doing). Then the results are compared to find the existing gaps between the formal and informal aspect. The results are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Formal versus informal aspect

Components	Albania	Kosovo
Purpose	Managers declared that the organizational goals, purpose and priorities were clearly stated. The employees declared the same.	Managers declared that the organizational goals, purpose and priorities were clearly stated. The employees declared the same for the organizational goals and purpose, but according to them the priorities were not clearly stated.
Structure	The managers and employees declared that the division of labor is helpful for the achievement of organizational goals and the structure of work is well designed. Both accepted that the division of work should be improved.	The managers and employees declared the division of labor is helpful for the achievement of the organizational goals and the structure of work is well designed. The managers said that the division of labor is efficient and flexible, while the employees said the opposite.
Relationship	The managers said that they have created a harmonious work environment and they have solved all the conflicts. The employees declared that some conflicts were not solved and the work environment is not harmonious because the relationship between the working unit is not a good one.	The managers said that very few conflicts exist in the organization due to the good relationships existing between working units and individuals. The employees declared that the relationships with the supervisors were not very good.
Reward	The managers declared that the reward system is transparent and	The managers declared that the reward system is transparent and

	equitable, while the employees declared the opposite.	equitable, while the employees declared the opposite.
Helpful mechanisms	It does exist compatibility between the answers of the managers and of the employees. The existing helpful mechanisms are effective.	It does not exist compatibility between the answers of the managers and of the employees. The managers declared that the existing helpful mechanisms are effective, while the employees said that they are not very effective.
Leadership	Even if the leadership style is authoritative, the employees are satisfied, because the leader is supportive and their opinion is always taken into consideration.	The employees declared that the leaders in many of the cases make more difficult their work. The managers declared that their leadership style is an open one, trying to support their employees.
Attitude toward change	Both the managers and the employees declared that the organization favor the change and has the ability to change.	Both the managers and the employees declared that the organization has the ability to change but first it has to accept that the change is necessary to adapt to the external environment.

In the Albanian public institution, the formal and informal aspect is not compatible for the “Relationship” and “Reward” component. In the Kosovo public institution, the formal and informal aspect are not compatible for the “Relationship”, “Leadership”, “Helpful Mechanisms” and “Reward” component.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study showed that the mean of each element was less than four (the neutral point), so in these public institutions did not exist serious problems regarding work division, clarity of organizational goals, leadership style, reward system, conflicts between individuals and working units, helpful mechanisms and ability to change. However some small problems were noticed:

- In the public institution in Kosovo, the organizational priorities were not fully understood by the employees. A public institution should have clear goals and priorities. The problem is that the managers declared that the priorities of the organization were clearly stated, while the employees did not think the same.
- The managers and the employees of the public institution in Kosovo and Albania stated that the work division is not perfect and should be improved. This is related in some way with the reward system. The managers declared that the reward system is transparent and equitable, while the employees declared the opposite. In the public institution in Kosovo and Albania in many cases, some employees are treated better due to their family relationships with the managers.
- In the public institution in Kosovo, the relationships between the working units were good, while the relationships between the employees and the managers were a little problematic. The opposite happened in the public institution in Albania. The employees had good relationships with the managers but the cooperation between the working units was not very good. This is explained by the cultural traits of the Albanian society. The power distance is high in Albania. This justifies the fact why the institution has a hierarchical structure and the employees accept the hierarchy. Albanian’s people are collectivist, long term committed to the group they belong. These elements make difficult the hiring and promotion of people based on their capabilities and competencies. Albanian society is masculine, and so each working unit wants to be the best and did not offer their help to the others.

It can be concluded that the organizational effectiveness is a little higher in the public institution in Albania than in

the public institution in Kosovo. To overcome these problems, I recommend to the Albanian and Kosovo institution:

Albanian institution: The most problematic component was reward. To overcome this problem the reward system should be transparent and the managers should ensure that each employee clearly understands the reward system. I recommend the use of specific procedures to solve the conflicts, like meeting the employees (to discuss and find the best solution for all). It is recommended to put deadlines for the solution of conflicts, especially the personal conflicts. If the personal conflicts are solved, the high managers should intervene. Finally, I recommend that the work division should be done based on meritocracy, in order that everyone can do the specific work better than the others.

Kosovo institution: The same recommendation prevails for the reward component and work division. In the meeting between the high managers and employees, the priorities of the organization should be highlighted in order that everyone can understand them. It is important that everyone participate actively in these meeting. The employees can be asked to express their opinion about the effectiveness of the existing helpful mechanisms. As the employees declared that the leaders intervene too much, it is better that they divide the problems in structured and unstructured. The last one requires more their intervention.

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